

Promoter induced rapid synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ molecular sieve in non-aqueous media using hexamethyleneimine template

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Abstract : $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ have been synthesized from non-aqueous media using hexamethyleneimine template in presence of sodium ions. The results show that the sodium catalyses the nucleation and crystallization process of the formation of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ molecular sieve. The material synthesized was characterized by XRD, SEM, carbon and nitrogen analysis, TG/DTA, FT-IR, ^{27}Al and ^{31}P MASNMR. The results show that the samples are highly crystalline. The presence of octahedral and tetrahedral sites are observed in ^{27}Al MASNMR, ^{31}P MASNMR gives only a single peak for tetrahedral phosphorous atoms.

Keywords : Non-aqueous media, molecular sieve, aluminophosphates.

Scientists at Union Carbide Corporation have synthesized a series of aluminophosphates ($\text{AlPO}_4\text{-n}$)¹ and element substituted aluminophosphate² molecular sieves such as silicon substituted (SAPO) and metal substituted (MAPO) examples. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-n}$ are generally prepared from aqueous hydrothermal systems through crystallization of an active aluminophosphate gel containing organic amine or quarternary ammonium templating agents¹⁻³, while zeolites⁴⁻⁶ can be synthesized from organic or mixed solvent systems in which water is a minor component. However, until now, few kinds of aluminophosphates have been synthesized⁷⁻¹⁰ from non-aqueous systems. The main problem faced in non-aqueous synthesis is that it takes more time for crystallization¹¹. Numerous efforts were taken to reduce the period^{12,13}. Here we have attempted with sodium ion as promoter¹⁴. The products were analyzed by various physicochemical techniques such as XRD, SEM, carbon and nitrogen analysis, TG/DTA, FT-IR, ^{27}Al and ^{31}P MASNMR spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

Alkalinity is an important variable during the hydrothermal synthesis of zeolite and can affect the crystallization greatly. However, it is not essential in aluminophosphate molecular sieves synthesis. Here, it is used as promoter. High alkalinity can shorten the induction period and accelerate crystallization. The decrease in induction period is attributed to the much greater concentration of reactants dissolved by the alkali. The nuclei will grow quickly because there are more numerous encounters between the precursor species in the solution phase. The enhanced rate of growth

after nucleation can be explained by the fact that a greater concentration of dissolved reactant in high alkalinity system allows faster transport to the surface of the growing crystals, higher concentration at the surface, and faster surface reaction to extend to the crystal lattice.

Besides the effect of alkalinity on crystallization, we also found that by tuning the system alkalinity, the formation of other crystals can be controlled efficiently. In high alkalinity system the crystallinity will decline after peaking with the extension of time. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ is a metastable phase in hydrothermal system, especially when the alkalinity is high. It will be re-resolved by hydroxy and be translated to a more stable phase, such as $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-22}$. In synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$, $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-22}$ is always accompanied by $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ molecular sieve. We found that formation of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-22}$ could be prevented by moderating the alkalinity or controlling crystallization time. When alkalinity was 0.3 $\text{Na}_2\text{O}/45\text{EG}$ formed even if the crystallization time extended to 5 days (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of sodium ions in $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ crystallization from non-aqueous media

Sl. no.	Gel molar composition	Duration of crystallization (days)	Product
1.	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : 1.8\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 : 4.5\text{HEM} : 45\text{EG}$	15	$\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$
2.	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : 1.8\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 : 0.30\text{Na}_2\text{O} : 4.5\text{HEM} : 45\text{EG}$	5	$\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$
3.	$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : 1.8\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 : 0.60\text{Na}_2\text{O} : 4.5\text{HEM} : 45\text{EG}$	3	$\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}^a$

Conditions : 200 °C, autogeneous pressure.

^aSmall impurities of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-22}$.

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized from non-aqueous media, (a) without sodium and (b) with sodium

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrograph of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized from non-aqueous media, (a) without sodium and (b) with sodium

The peak positions of the X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) pattern of the $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ so synthesized from non-aqueous media with sodium are similar to the XRD pattern of the $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ prepared without sodium in the same media (Fig. 1), although peak intensities differ. The as-synthesized form of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$, synthesized using hexamethylenimine from non-aqueous medium without sodium contained three templates per unit cell. However, $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized using the same template in non-aqueous medium with sodium contained three template molecules per unit cell along with six ethylene glycol molecules ($C = 23.90\%$ and $N = 3.05\%$). This is sterically possible if one template is packed tight over the other two along the c -direction of the unit cell. The template is less tightly packed in the case of the $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized in non-aqueous medium without sodium promoter. Elemental analysis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ of both the

samples show the same as $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : 0.99 \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) shows that the $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ exists as hexagonal morphology (Fig. 2) in non-aqueous media without sodium are in $3.2 \mu\text{m}$ particle size. However, the samples with sodium are in spheroidal morphology with $10 \mu\text{m}$ particle size with uniform particle size. The IR spectrum (Fig. 3) shows three bands at $1215\text{--}725$, $700\text{--}645$, 565cm^{-1} , which are characteristic of aluminophosphate molecular sieves. The asymmetric stretching vibrations of the $\text{P}\text{--}\text{O}\text{--}\text{Al}$ unit occur at 1215 , 1130 , 725cm^{-1} and symmetric stretching vibrations of $\text{P}\text{--}\text{O}\text{--}\text{Al}$ is at 700 and 645cm^{-1} . The band at 565cm^{-1} arises from vibration of the characteristic aluminophosphate framework. The peak positions did not change with sodium of crystallization. The $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ sample was subjected to thermal analysis (Fig. 4). In non-aqueous media samples without sodium are loss, 15.98% from room temperature to $610 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the same for samples with sodium loss 16.24% . This mass loss corresponds to the amount of organic molecules and water adsorbed by $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$. The exothermic peaks at 360 and $474 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for without sodium samples and 252 , 326 , 402 , $546 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for with sodium ions are caused by a oxidative decomposition of the template.

$\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ was calcined at $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at 10^{-3} Torr for 1 h and water adsorption experiments on the calcined sample showed that it was a type I adsorption isotherm and indicated that the amount of adsorbed water was $17\% \text{ m/m}$ for non-aqueous media samples with sodium.

Fig. 3. FT-IR spectra of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized from non-aqueous media, (a) without sodium and (b) with sodium

Fig. 4. TGA (A) and DTA (B) of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized from non-aqueous media (a) without sodium and (b) with sodium

Fig. 5. ^{27}Al (a) and ^{31}P (b) MASNMR of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized from non-aqueous media with sodium

The ^{27}Al MASNMR spectra (Fig. 5) of as-synthesized $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ shows a resonance at δ 32.03, which is indicative of aluminium coordinated and linked to four oxygen atoms¹⁵. Another peak at δ 2.54 has also appeared. This may be due to the aluminium present in octahedral position. However, the $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ samples synthesized from aqueous media did not have this peak. Another peak at δ -27.35 is due to the side bands of the aluminium spectra. The ^{31}P spectrum of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ (a sharp resonance at δ -31.51) is due to the presence of phosphorous in tetrahedral position^{16,17}.

Conclusion :

Alkalinity can effect the $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ crystallization greatly. Less time needed for crystallization in higher caustic system, but $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-22}$ will still probably form. By adjusting alkalinity or controlling crystallization time, the formation of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-22}$ can be prevented. The synthesized material were characterized by XRD, SEM, TG/DTA, carbon and nitrogen analysis, FT-IR, ^{27}Al and ^{31}P MASNMR techniques. XRD shows the crystallinity of the $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$. This is also confirmed by SEM photograph. The samples shows spheroidal morphology with 10 μm particle size, which differ from the samples without sodium. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ synthesized in non-aqueous medium with sodium contained three template molecules per unit cell along with six ethylene glycol molecules but sodium free sample did not contain any ethylene glycol. TG/DTA gives the weight loss due to the loss of water and template molecules. FT-IR analysis shows the framework vibrations. ^{27}Al and ^{31}P MASNMR results show the presence of two different types of aluminium atoms which are due to the cation present in tetrahedral and octahedral positions and one type of phosphorous atom present in tetrahedral positions.

Experimental

$\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ from non-aqueous system with sodium promoter was synthesized as follows : To 6.05 g of aluminium isopropoxide (98%, Aldrich, India) thoroughly mixed with 45.50 g of ethylene glycol (98%, s.d. fine, India). 7.27 g of hexamethyleneimine was added dropwise. 0.351 g of sodium hydroxide (99%, s.d. fine, India) was added to the above mixture. Then 6.024 g of orthophosphoric acid was added dropwise to the resulting gel and stirred well. The final gel having molar composition $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : 1.8\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 : 0.25\text{Na}_2\text{O} : 4.5\text{HEM} : 4.5\text{EG}$ was charged into a teflon lined stainless steel autoclave. Crystallization was carried out for 5 days at 473 K. The resulting product was removed and washed with distilled water several times and dried at 383

K for 8 h. The solid was subjected to various physicochemical characterization.

The sample synthesized during the course of the work was analyzed for qualitative identification by X-ray powder diffraction (Rigaku, Model D/MAX III VC, Japan; Ni filtered $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation, $\lambda = 1.5404 \text{ \AA}$; graphite crystal monochromator; computer controlled automated diffractometer). The morphologies of the aluminophosphate synthesized was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL, JSM 5200). The framework region ($400\text{--}1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the synthesized aluminophosphates were analyzed using a Nicolet 60SXB FT-IR instrument in the diffuse reflectance mode using a 1 : 300 ratio of the sample to KBr mixture. Simultaneous TG/DTA analysis of the crystalline phases were performed on an automatic derivatograph (Setaram TG-DTA 92). The thermograms were recorded in flow of nitrogen with heating rate 10 K/min. MASNMR spectra were recorded in the solid state with a Bruker DRX 500 spectrometer operating at a field of 11.7 Tesla. ^{27}Al spectra were recorded at a frequency of 130.3 MHz, with a pulse length of 2 μs and a spinning speed of 3–5 KHz. ^{31}P spectra were recorded at a frequency of 202.45 MHz with a pulse length of 1.5 μs and the recycle delay was 4 s. 1 M $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and 1 M H_3PO_4 solutions (for aluminium and phosphorous) were used as standards.

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